

Introduction

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The COVID19 pandemic is a most dramatic challenge that affects the entire World. Almost two years of restrictions and social distancing have changed the way we live, work and interact with each other. Despite the closure of schools and universities, the adoption of distance learning measures has allowed to sustain the educational system in most countries, but has had deep consequences on the overall educational experience of the younger generations. Similarly, early career astronomers at all levels (PhD and post-doc) have been forced to adapt to a new working scenario that presented numerous challenges. The “classical” approaches needed to build a solid and gratifying professional profile, to create a network of collaborations, and to communicate the scientific results went through a complete revision which required (and still requires) creativity, strong commitment and support from senior astronomers, supervisors and mentors. At ESO, we felt the responsibility to invest our energy and creativity to put in place a channel to allow excellent young researchers to show the results of their scientific work.

Thanks to the positive experience of the ESO Cosmic Duologues series [1], we have now learned to which extent on-line seminars can be an efficient practice to engage and reach out to the astronomical community even under the severe restrictions imposed by the pandemic. As part of the ESO science activities, the Office for Science in the Directorate of Science therefore organised a new series of seminars called the *Hypatia Colloquium*, dedicated to early career scientists. This book collects the scientific contributions of most of the speakers of the first series in the form of proceedings.

The call for abstracts

At the beginning of November 2020, ESO released a call for abstracts through which PhD students and early post-docs (maximum 3 years from the PhD) working in any field of theoretical and observational astronomy and astrophysics, without any limitations of their nationality or host country, were invited to apply to be nominated as speaker of an Hypatia Colloquium. The new series was designed to host two seminars per event. This translated into 42 slots available for the talks. The deadline to send the application was set to November 30, 2020. In less than a month, ESO received 334 valid applications from young astronomers around the world.

The extremely positive reaction and participation from young astronomers already witness a strong desire to break the walls of confinement in which the pandemic has contained our scientific life and explore new spaces to express talent and creativity. The selection of the top speakers was done by an ad-hoc committee composed of ESO astronomers from both Garching and Vitacura, based on the scientific quality of the submitted abstracts

and the speaker’s contribution to the work. The 42 selected speakers were contacted towards mid-December and the full programme released before Christmas 2020.

The complete programme of the talks can be found on the dedicated web page*. The programme page reports the name and a picture of the speakers together with the title of the talk and the date and time of each event. By clicking on the title of the talk it is also possible to download the full abstract of the talk and a curriculum vitae of the speaker.

Figure 1: Distribution of gender and year of the PhD of the speakers of the Hypatia Colloquium series. The call was released on November 2020 meaning that all speakers whose PhD is planned in 2021 and 2022 where still PhD students at the time of giving the talk.

We show in Figure 1 the distribution of the gender (left pie-plot) and year of PhD (right histogram) of the speakers selected for the Hypatia Colloquium 2021. It is worth to note that the call was released in November 2020 and the program published at the end of the same year. Hence, at the time of giving their talk, half of the speakers had not yet completed their PhD. Impressive fact when considering the scientific quality of the talks!

The new series

The talks were scheduled on Tuesdays at 3pm Garching (Germany) time from February 2 to July 27, 2021 (except once per month, when there was an ESO Cosmic Duologue). The format of this series foresees two 20 min-long talks, each followed by questions and discussion. Most of the seminars were co-chaired by an ESO Student and an ESO Fellow.

The seminars were entirely hosted on-line using the video conferencing tool Zoom and live streamed on the Hypatia Colloquium YouTube channel†. Attendees could register to the series using a web form. Registered participants were able to attend the seminars and interact with the speakers via the Zoom meeting. Alternatively, the community was invited to attend the live events on the dedicated YouTube page. All YouTube attendees could ask questions during the live event using the Live Chat

*<https://www.eso.org/sci/meetings/garching/hypatia-colloquium/program.html>

†<https://www.youtube.com/c/HypatiaColloquium/featured>

Figure 2: Snapshot of the YouTube channel of the Hypatia Colloquium. All the talks of the series of 2021 are available on the dedicated playlist.

on YouTube (or using a web form or by email if they preferred). All the video recordings of the live events, including the content of the live chat, are available on YouTube[‡]. We show in Figure 2 a snapshot of the front page of the Hypatia Colloquium YouTube channel.

The channel analytics clearly attests the success of the series. While each event was followed live by a total of 40 to 60 participants equally spread between Zoom and YouTube, the videos record (at the time of writing this introduction in October 2021) a total of almost 4 600 views. While the numbers are already quite impressive, it is when watching the seminars that the real quality and impact of the series can be fully appreciated. With the Hypatia Colloquium, ESO allowed the young generation of astronomers to paint a remarkable and unique portrait of the excellence of the science presently done by the early career astronomers. The videos available on-line represent an extraordinary and exploitable treasure and resource of talent.

[The support to the young generation](#)

The final words should be spent for all the young as-

tronomers who are struggling during these challenging times. It is not easy to maintain the focus and motivation when such a dramatic event like the COVID19 pandemic is putting our (and our beloved's) health, life and safeness in great danger. Science is a wonderful endeavour which requires dedication and sacrifice but always pays back through astonishing discoveries that reveal the beauty hidden in our Universe.

Universities, research institutes, senior astronomers and mentors at all levels have now the responsibility to build the infrastructures and to redesign evaluation and hiring processes, in order to face the new reality with a modern attitude, adequate to the times and able to create the space for the creativity of the youngest generations to bloom and grow. At the same time, we must all help each other to remember that gratitude, humility, passion and professionalism are key ingredients to translate our efforts into knowledge for the future generations.

[Reference](#)

- [1] Beccari, G., & Boffin, H. M. J. 2020, ESO Messenger, 181, 34

[‡]The links are all available on the web page of the programme